

GC-MS and HPTLC analysis of constituents of an unexploded bomb

S. P. Sharma^a and S. C. Lahiri^{b*}

^aChemistry Division, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata-700 014, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235, India

E-mail : sujitelahiri@yahoo.com

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In this study *N*-methyl-*N*-2,4,6-tetranitroaniline (tetryl) was detected from an unexploded bomb produced during World War-II, by GC-MS technique using a suitable low column temperature parameters. Quantification of tetryl was made by HPTLC technique. A non polar solvent system is used for developing the spots. The developed spots were scanned by the densitometer using the light beam (240 nm) of length greater than the diameter of the spot.

A large number of ingredients like nitroglycerine, TNT, pentaerythritol tetranitrate (PETN), nitrocellulose, tetryl (*N*-methyl-*N*-2,4,6-tetranitroaniline) were widely used as explosives. They are the ingredients for the manufacture of bombs during World War-II¹. With the advent of cyclonite (RDX), PETN, the use of tetryl has been considerably reduced and withdrawn in the USA¹. However, the paper presented here is the report of an attempt to identify and quantify the ingredients used for the manufacture of bombs used in the second world war using GC-MS and HPTLC^{1,2}. Thus the investigation is relevant to the forensic science.

Case history :

During the second world war, the British military base at Andaman and Nicobar islands was subjected to heavy bombing by Germany. However, some of the bombs fell in the marshy lands and did not explode. One such bomb was recovered and collected by digging the soils by Bomb Detection and Disposal Squad, Ministry of Defence, Government of India. It was kept as an exhibit in the military base at Kanchrapara. The sample was collected from the dismantled bomb for analysis.

Results and discussion

The GC-MS at higher temperatures conclusively shows that the spectra determined was exclusively due to the decomposition product of tetryl and no other ingredients were present. The total ion chromatogram (TIC) of the standard tetryl and the sample were identical and Rt value was 11.17 minute. The mass spectra of the peak, Rt value 11.17 minute was confirmed from the literature^{1,3} and from *m/z* values of the fragments as the decomposition product of *N*-methyl-*N*-2,4,6-tetranitroaniline (tetryl) which is '*N*-methylpicramide'. No other ingredients appeared to be present.

Table 1. The GC-MS data at 70 eV

<i>m/z</i> Values of the sample at Rt 11.17 of TIC	<i>m/z</i> Values of the standard tetryl at Rt 11.17 of TIC	<i>m/z</i> Values of the standard tetryl in direct probe
30	30	30
41	41	41
46	46	46
50	50	50
62	62	62
75	75	75
76	76	76
91	91	91
102	102	102
118	118	118
137	137	137
149	149	149
166	166	166
178	178	178
194	194	194
211	211	211
224	224	224
241	241	241
242	242	242

The presence of 'tetryl' was further confirmed from mass-spectra (direct insertion probe). The temperature range was 35–220°C, the rate of temperature increase was 120°C/min. Tetryl vapour as such was detected up to 75–80°C above which it decomposed into picramide. The combination continued up to 190°C above which picramide also decomposed. The spectral data were summarized in Table 1. The quantitative estimation of tetryl was made using HPTLC. The area of the individual spots was measured by densitometer using 240 nm wavelength beam. Table 2 shows the area of the spots against weight of standard tetryl. The weight vs area curve showed that it is linear up to 7.824 µg having area 421.8. Therefore, in the calculation of percentage of tetryl, only the linear zone i.e. up to 7.824 µg was

used. The sample were measured and the area of the individual spots and percentages are presented in Table 3. The average values was found to be 98.53%. It can be concluded that pure tetryl was used for the manufacture of bomb dropped in Andaman and Nicobar islands. However it was not possible to determine the 'taggants' which may be present in very small amounts. The mechanism of the formation of *N*-methylpicramide as hydrolysis product of tetryl suggested by Tammi *et al.*³ is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 2 Area vs weight of tetryl in the standard sample

Sl no	Volume (μl)	Weight (μg)	Area (arbitrary units related to figure)
1	3	0.978	54.3
2	6	1.956	108.1
3	9	2.934	162.2
4	12	3.912	216.8
5	15	4.89	271.4
6	18	5.868	325.6
7	21	6.846	370.2
8	24	7.824	421.8
9	30	9.78	457.4
10	60	19.56	730.7
11	90	29.34	1055.1
12	120	39.12	1236.4

Table 3 Area vs weight of the sample

Sl no	Volume (μl)	Weight (μg)	Area (arbitrary units)	% of tetryl	Average
1	3	0.744	40.6	98.64	
2	6	1.488	81.9	99.4	98.53%
3	9	2.232	120.1	97.57	

However *N*-methylpicramide may also be formed by hydrogen abstraction (Fig. 1). But it has not been verified by increasing ion source pressure.

Experimental

Sample collection Sample was collected from a part which was a cylindrical shaped rod with a central hole for insertion of the detonator. The cylinder was with a wrapper having 'Made in Germany' 1939, inscription.

Qualitative analysis The compounds were identified by GC-MS. The solvent used in the experiment (acetone, benzene and diethylether) were of HPLC grade (E. Merck, India).

The standard tetryl was taken from High Energy Materials Research Laboratory, Pune, India. The standard solution of tetryl was made by taking 0.0163 g in 50 ml acetone and the sample solution contained 0.0124 g of the sample in 50 ml acetone. The analysis was carried out by MS and GC of Finnigan Thermoquest using the following parameters:

Fig. 1 Mechanisms of formation of *N*-methylpicramide

Column-capillary used was RTX-5MS, 15 meters, 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 microns coating. Oven temperature was programmed keeping the initial value at 65°C and final temperature at 240°C with 15°C/min increments. The injector port temperature was 170°C with split mode having split ratio 10. Helium was the carrier gas with a flow rate of 1.2 ml/min at constant flow mode. The interface temperature was 180°C. Injection volume was 1 μl (microliter). The source temperature was 140°C. Other parameters were – energy 70 eV, solvent delay 7.0 min and mass range scanned between 25–400 amu. At low temperature i.e. below 130°C elution of the 'tetryl' was not observed in the column used in the present investigation. Naturally, one had to carry out the experiment at higher temperatures where tetryl decomposed (m.p. of tetryl 129.5°C) and the spectra determined was exclusively due to its decomposition product.

Quantitative analysis Quantitative analysis of the tetryl present in the sample was done by HPTLC. The HPTLC analysis was carried out by using Desaga HPTLC system with CD-60 densitometer. The E. Merck's precoated TLC plates of 80–100 mesh of size 20 cm × 20 cm and 0.25 mm layer thickness were used. The standard tetryl solution and the sample solution was spotted on a 20 × 20 cm² plate keeping 15 mm margin at the bottom and 10 mm each at right and left side. The standard solution of tetryl was spotted by automatic spotting system. Each spot was given by 3 μl/cycle with a break of 5 s in between two cycle. Standard tetryl were spotted at 12 positions having volumes 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 30, 60, 90 and 120 μl.

The sample was spotted at 6 positions having volumes 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 μl. The plates were developed in a CAMMAG developing chamber by the solvent mixture of benzene and diethyl ether in the ratio 3 : 1. The developed plates were scanned by the densitometer using the light beam (240 nm) of length 10 mm and width of 0.25 mm as it fully covered the spot areas during scanning of the spots.

The area of the individual spot was measured by the densitometer using 240 nm wave length beam. Table 2 shows the area of the spots of standard tetryl of different concentrations. The sample spots were also measured and the area of the individual spots are given in Table 3.

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